

Preparation and characterization of new lanthanum-functionalized adsorbents from a residual lignocellulosic biomass and their use in arsenic adsorption

Mendoza-Castillo D.I.^{1,2}, di Bitonto L.³, Reynel-Ávila H.E.^{1,2}, Milella A.⁴, Durán-Valle C.J.⁵, Bonilla-Petriciolet A.¹, Pastore C.^{3*}

¹ Instituto Tecnológico de Aguascalientes, Av. Adolfo López Mateos #1801 Ote., Aguascalientes 20256, Mexico

² Cátedras CONACYT Jóvenes Investigadores, Ciudad de México, 03940, México

³ Water Research Institute (IRSA), National Research Council (CNR), via F. de Blasio 5, 70132, Bari, Italy

⁴ Dipartimento di Chimica, Università degli Studi di Bari (UNIBA), via E. Orabona 4, 70126, Bari, Italy

⁵ Department of Organic and Inorganic Chemistry, Universidad de Extremadura, Av. Elvas, 06006, Badajoz, Spain

*corresponding author: e-mail: carlo.pastore@ba.irsna.cnr.it

Abstract

Water pollution control is a relevant issue worldwide. In particular, the contents of arsenic (As) dissolved in the water extracted from the subsoil in several regions around the world, including Mexico, may exceed the concentration guidelines established by the World Health Organization (WHO). The natural presence of this geogenic pollutant becomes an environmental and public health problem. This situation implies that around four million people have the risk to consume water polluted with arsenic concentrations higher than 10 µg/L. Under this perspective, the reduction of As concentrations in polluted effluents and water supply sources for human use and consumption constitutes one of the priority environmental challenges. An effective method for this purpose is the adsorption process. In particular, the preparation of adsorbents from waste materials is an alternative to improve the cost-effectiveness tradeoff of conventional removal methods. Lignocellulosic wastes have been successfully utilized as precursors to obtain adsorbents to remove different water pollutants due to their high carbon content, low cost and availability in nature. Therefore, this study has focused on the preparation of lanthanum-functionalized adsorbents to remove arsenic from aqueous solution using avocado seeds as precursor. Avocado seeds is an important lignocellulosic waste generated in Mexico and other countries by the food industry where this waste biomass is usually discarded. Carbon-based adsorbents were obtained via pyrolysis of this biomass and it was further functionalized with lanthanum using different experimental conditions. These adsorbents were characterized by X-ray diffraction, FTIR and XPS and their arsenic uptakes were determined at batch conditions. Arsenic adsorption capacities of lanthanum based adsorbents ranged from 2.5 to 4.9 mg/g. These adsorption capacities were higher than those obtained for the adsorbent without lanthanum. In fact, an increment of the arsenic removal up to 425 % was observed on the modified adsorbents.

Keywords: adsorption, arsenic, lignocellulosic waste, water purification

Acknowledges

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778168